

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Tantalum(V) with Mepazine Hydrochloride

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Manuscript received 9 January 1991, revised 22 July 1991, accepted 7 February 1992

Tantalum forms a mixed ligand yellow coloured complex with pyrogallol and mepazine hydrochloride [10-{(1-methyl-3-piperidyl) methyl} phenothiazine hydrochloride] (MH) which results in bathochromic shift, increase in sensitivity, stability and free from interference of associated ions particularly niobium.

Results and Discussion

Maximum absorbance was achieved in 0.05–0.09 *M* sulphuric acid and an acid concentration of 0.07 *M* was chosen for all subsequent work. Among various solvents tried chloroform was found to be most suitable solvent as the extractant had maximum sensitivity and stability. Maximum absorbance values were obtained with 0.5–1.5 ml of 2% pyrogallol and 8–10 ml of 0.4% MH in chloroform. Therefore 1 ml of 2% pyrogallol and 8 ml of 0.4% MH in chloroform were used for the work.

Beer's law was valid over the tantalum concentration range of 0.8–14 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $5.97 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.03 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative error in the determination of $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of tantalum were 0.018 and $\pm 0.6\%$ respectively. The composition of the complex as determined by Job's method³ of continuous variation and equilibrium-shift method⁴ indicated 1:2:2 stoichiometry with respect to tantalum, pyrogallol and MH.

The extent of interference of the cations and anions were determined by measuring the absorbance of $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of tantalum and various amounts of diverse ions. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance values was considered to be tolerable. The tolerance limits of various ions are as follows (figures in parenthesis represent tolerance limit in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): Al^{III} (3000), Mn^{II} (2000), Ni^{II} (400), Co^{II} (100), Cu^{II} (150), Nb^{V} (140), Pt^{IV} (100), U^{VI}

(50), W^{VI} (20), chloride (1600), bromide (1500), iodide (800), nitrate (1000), phosphate (1200), sulphate (4000), acetate (1200), oxalate (4000) and tartarate (2000). EDTA and ascorbic acid do not interfere. The tolerance limit for Fe^{III} and V^V were 250 and $50 \mu g ml^{-1}$ respectively in presence of 2 ml of 20% ascorbic acid as masking agent.

The proposed method was applied to the determination of tantalum in some mineral samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TANTALUM(V) IN MINERAL SAMPLES*

Sample	% Ta_2O_5 Certified value	% Ta_2O_5 Found	Standard deviation
IGS-33	5.340	5.365	0.016
IGS-34	49.920	49.956	0.012

*Average value of five determinations.

Experimental

A Beckman model DB spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Standard tantalum(v) solution was prepared from tantalum pentoxide¹. A 0.4% mepazine hydrochloride solution was prepared in chloroform and stored in a refrigerator and a 2% aqueous solution of pyrogallol was freshly prepared.

To an aliquot of the stock solution (containing upto $140 \mu g$ of tantalum) were added 0.7 M H_2SO_4 (1 ml), 2% pyrogallol (1 ml) and 0.4% MH in

chloroform (6 ml) and the mixture was shaken vigorously for 2 min and the layers were allowed to separate for 5 min. The chloroform phase was separated and the aqueous phase was shaken with 0.4% MH in chloroform (2 ml). The combined chloroform phase was dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), the volume made upto 10 ml with chloroform and its absorbance was measured at 400 nm against the reagent blank.

In the procedure for the determination of tantalum in mineral samples, a known quantity of the mineral sample was brought into solution². To the above solution (containing upto $140 \mu g$ of tantalum) was added 20% ascorbic acid (2 ml) to mask iron(III) and the amount of tantalum in the sample was determined by following the above procedure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Bayer AG, Leverkusen, West Germany for the supply of MH and to Dr. B. K. Balaji, Atomic Minerals Division, Bangalore for supplying mineral samples.

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